

Need To Think Before We Act React or Use Social Media

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Abstract

Social media has strongly influenced the people and the whole world. It is a technology that helps the people to interact and connect by producing, sharing, and sometimes exchanging ideas, images, videos and many more over the internet in virtual communities'. From making connections through worldwide connectivity, from online businesses to digital marketing, from creating brand loyalty to awareness, social media has tremendously affected our lives. We feel blessed to have social media in our lives. But it is a fact too that for millions of years, our forefathers formed important social links and shared information through them. So at the most basic level, social media is not changing humankind so much as tapping into what we have always been. Online social networks are a new way to do an old thing. In different places in different times horses, ships, trains, and planes delivered the information to maintain and build connectivity. Then came era of Telegram, Radio, Telephone and Telecommunication satellites to quicken the pace of communication. We always have been linked to others. What is different about the present scenario of social media is that now we have the ability to connect to vastly more people over greater distance than ever before more immediately and more instantaneously. Whether this will enhance or debase our humanity in the long run is an open question. Nobody can deny the fact that using social media excessively can cause disastrous issues, which can have adverse impact on our lives.

Keywords: Social Media, Technology, Virtual, Digital, Satellite, Debase

Introduction

Social media is an online platform which people use to build social network and social relations with other people by using various online applications such as Facebook, Facebook Messenger, Twitter, Skype, Viber, Instagram, YouTube, WhatsApp, Snapchat etc. Communication is fundamental to the existence and survival of humans as well as to an organization. It is a process of creating and sharing ideas, information, views, facts, feelings from one place, person or group to another. Man has always an urge to connect with people, to communicate in order to express himself, to release pent up emotions and to be visible in the society either with face to face conversation or virtually like in the present scenario of social media. Social media refers to a computer-based technology that facilitates the sharing of ideas, thoughts, and information through virtual networks and communities. Social media is internet-based and gives users quick electronic communication of content, such as personal information, documents, videos, and photos. It comes up as a big boon for the people as it gives them a platform to connect globally to new people, to raise some issues of importance as the feedback on them are really instant and immediate. Many people become internet sensation and popular overnight by uploading their content online on social media. Social Media is a prevalent medium in today's scenario because of its ability to transfer information and communicate with people worldwide using the internet connection. We have seen how social media networking sites make it easier for people spread across the globe to connect. The people who spend more time on these sites are usually young and adolescents as it is a kind of utopia for them. But are we aware about its consequences and Do we really pay heed how much these social networking sites impacts us negatively? Do we really think that the excessive use of internet and social networking sites can really ruin our lives? If not then it is a matter of great concern and need to be addressed an issues that seems to be trivial but actually they can harm our lives and can affect a person emotionally, mentally and even physically.

Major problems with social media

Wastage of time

One cannot deny the fact that many users spend lot of time using social sites. Once a person is addicted of it, it is difficult to get rid of this addiction. The social media companies usually keeps adding new features to make it more alluring and fascinating to the users and when one becomes its frequent and continuous visitor, he or she becomes addictive of it and it's really hard to resist its temptations. Social media addiction can be seen not only in adolescents but the people of all age groups nowadays. As a result of it laziness and procrastination become habits of the users which in turn causes stress, anxiety and unnecessary worries.

Conversation in the Dark

Social media is like ‘conversation in the dark’. It can be difficult to read people, no matter how plain and straightforward their typed words may be. That little, telling inflection of voice that gives away true intent face to face is missing in a tweet or Facebook comment. There are many imposters on social sites that make many people their prey. Online frauds, Identity thefts, scams, bluffing are very common offences associated with it.

Nothing remains private or privacy Issues

In this virtual world people are obsessed with posting everything on social media. Posting pictures of where you are going, eating, attending family functions, personal pictures from the galleries, posting details regarding personal, professional life, people have made their personal security vulnerable by themselves only. There is no guarantee that everybody is happy by seeing your personal growth or happiness. Even there is no surety that nobody will take advantage of the pictures, personal information or data that we post on social media. There are many criminal minded people who morphed pictures and videos and then used them against the victim. These kinds of posts may give birth to major problems like stress or anxiety and even serious issues like suicides.

Cyber bullying

Cyber bullying is one of the major issues that people encounter on social media, messaging platforms and mobile phones. It aims at frequently scaring, angering or blackmailing the targeted person. It takes place in different forms such as posting embarrassing pictures or video clips of someone on social media by posting hurtful, awkward or embarrassing messages, pictures, video clips of someone through fake accounts and then demanding money or other unfair favours by blackmailing the victims or defaming their reputation. The outcome of such bullying is so extreme that sometimes many people commit suicide and ended their lives. Cybercrimes in India have increased four times in the past few years. In 2016, 12317 cases of cybercrime were registered and in 2020 this number increases to 50,035. This means that India registered 136 cybercrime cases every day in 2020, according to the National Crime Records Bureau (NCRB). In 2020, the state of Uttar Pradesh in India had the highest number of reported cybercrime compared to the rest of the country with over 11000 cases registered with the authorities. Presently, in India there is a huge increase in cyber bullying cases according to Child Rights and You (CRY). One in three adults gets bullied every day and most of them are aged between 13 to 18 years. According to National Crime Records Bureau, there are 36% increase in cyber stalking and cyber bullying cases in India.

Anxiety and Depression

Man wants to connect with people and with the introduction of this young technology of social media, many of us rely on Facebook, Instagram, Snapchat, Twitter, YouTube etc. to connect with the people online. No doubt, these platforms of social media have benefits but their flip side can't be ignored. Social media connect us virtually with friends, family etc. but it can't be a replacement of face to face connection with our loved ones. In fact these platforms connect us through internet but disconnect us from the real world. Spending too much time on social media can be a reason of stress, anxiety loneliness or even depression. This affects the quality of our lives as it make us ,pensive discontented and lonely which are not healthy signs for our mental peace and health.

Identity Crisis

People who overuse social media can be a victim of Identity crisis. Repeated exposure to social networking sites is causing identity crisis among the users, a leading scientist has warned. Barron's Greenfield, a professor of Pharmacology at Oxford University said, Facebook and Twitter have created generation obsessed with themselves who has short attention spans and a childlike desire for constant feedback on their social media posts. She further adds, it is almost as if people are living in a world that is not a real, but a world where what counts is what people think of you or can click on you. The growth of rapid internet friendships as well as excessive use of online games can affects the brain.

Cyberbullicide

It's a kind of suicide that people commits because of cyber bullying. Social media is one of the major platforms often used for cyberbullying. It leads to suicide or suicidal tendencies among adolescents. Victims of cyberbullying are at a higher risk of experiencing self-harm and suicidal behaviors'. Students who face is bullying or cyberbullicide are twice more likely to attempt suicides.

Facebook Depression

Facebook depression is another drawback of spending too much time on Facebook and being exposed to the intensity of online activities of others that one starts to exhibit depressive symptoms. It often encourage attitude that is not good for mental health such as unhealthy comparisons, jealousy, fake life style just to look perfect to the people on social networking sites.

Social Media Syndromes

The addiction of social media give rise to many disorders that impacts and adversely impacts the mental health and peace of the users .The excessive use of social media disconnects the user from the social and family life in the real sense .There are many social media syndromes that are associated with the excessive use of social media platforms. Some of them are:

Phubbing

Phubbing means ignoring once family members or friends by constantly being on the phone. It impacts relationships as the people avoid face to face conversation and prefer online chatting or calls. One may be termed as rude or arrogant because of this habit. It is also threat to a smooth and meaningful existence.

FOMO

It's a social anxiety rooted in the fact that a person might miss out on fun or an important event when they are absent. This is the reason people spend hours on social media platforms which in terms lead to mobile addiction.

Obsession to Look Picture Perfect

This can be seen in so many social media users with the trend of posting so many selfies and videos on social media. The users are usually obsess to look picture perfect in every selfie they click. Such people tend to obsess over their bodies and may even go to the extreme of getting surgeries to look perfect.

Social Media Anxiety Disorder

It is very common among the users of social media and can cause harm to physical and mental will being of an individual. Adding unknown people to social media accounts, spending ample of time on social networking sites, a sense of anxiety develops when there are no comments on likes on the shared post .Checking the number of followers and avoiding family or friends when they are around can create issues of low self- esteem, body image issues or a sense of loneliness

Hacking, misinformation spread of rumors that sometimes lead to online rage and hatred are among the issues that the users encounter using social media.

BASIC SECURITY TIPS IN BRIEF

Log off and turn off: If you don't need to be online while using your computer, then don't be. If you aren't using your computer, then turn it off. Going off-line or powering off does not eliminate the risk of being hacked but does significantly reduce the danger.

Backup Your Data: If your data is backed up frequently, you are less vulnerable to ransomware or a virus.

Understand that Social Media can impact your off-line life

Social Media is an increasingly popular source of information about individuals. You may be analyzed and judged by potential employers, renters, school administrators, romantic interests, loan officers, and so on, based on your social media activity.

Don't trust pirated materials: Downloading a large file from a stranger who doesn't own the Rights to it, is asking for trouble.

Delete apps you don't use: Think of apps as little spies who live in your phone. The fewer of them, the better. If you can live without an app, get rid of it.

Don't share everything about yourself on social media: Criminals, creeps, and trolls can exploit personal information you post online.

Update Software Often and Always: Don't ignore prompts for software updates. Software companies are locked in an endless war with hackers, and you want the fixes and upgrades they fight back with.

Don't fill out online questionnaires: Many websites exist just to suck up data from visitors.

Don't make it easier for data brokers by answering every question a site asks. Don't fill in personal details unless you really need something on the other side of that form.

Beware of USB drives: They are common carriers of malware.

Think before sexting: Sending private sexually explicit photos or messages are dangerous for several reasons. If you're tempted, pause and consider possible consequences before you do it.

Use strong passwords: Don't use common words or phrases. The longer it is, the better it would be.

Include random numbers and symbols. Change passwords often. Don't use the same password for multiple accounts.

Use two-step authentication: Adding one small step can be a big leap for personal security. Don't be stupid. Recognize and accept that you can be a victim of cybercrime or online harassment. Everyone is a target.

Conclusion

Acknowledging serious problems does not mean we must fear, hate, or reject social media. A bit of awareness and personal dedication to good thinking can be enough to significantly elevate and make safer the social media experience. It should not surprise us that billions have been drawn to one form of social media or another. We are primates, social creatures who find it not only enjoyable but also necessary to form social bonds and maintain near-constant communication with other. People need people; and social media feeds the hunger, to some degree. These various platforms help us do what we must: communicate, share feelings, gossip, teach, learn, brag, envy, hate, and love. The advantages and disadvantages of social media cannot be denied. It depends upon the users how they use it smartly. Now, it is the responsibility and accountability of the social media users to think when to act and react on social media and how to use it in a positive manner. If an individual feels that social media is coming in between his/her personal space, then it would be suggested to take a break from it. After all, when you correctly use something, then it fails to hamper your work or life; instead, it productively enhances your life by a creative, healthy environment and inculcating positivity around. Last but not least social media can act as a boon or a bane depends on its use. Therefore, it must be handled with care and wisdom.

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Social media sites leading to identity crises

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